

NEEDS ASSESSMENT RESULTS OF THE FEDERATION OF DAY CARE WORKERS OF IRIGA CITY

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the educational and professional development needs of the Federation of Day Care Workers of Iriga City for Academic Year 2015–2016. Using a descriptive research design, survey questionnaires and informal interviews were administered to forty-seven (47) day care workers under the supervision of the City Social Welfare and Development Office. Results revealed that the respondents needed support in three main areas: personal development, life skills enhancement, and educational improvement. In particular, teachers expressed a strong need for assistance in the use of educational technology, the development of new teaching strategies, and the application of interactive learning activities such as games, songs, and storytelling.

Based on the findings, an Enrichment Program was designed to deliver monthly capacity-building sessions focusing on language development, computer literacy, financial literacy, health and wellness, and personal formation. The study highlights the importance of needs-based assessment in the formulation of effective extension and outreach programs that enhance the teaching competencies of early childhood educators and promote sustainable community development.

Keywords: Needs Assessment, Day Care Workers, Educational Improvement, Community Extension

I. Introduction

La Consolacion College, Iriga City maintains the Mother Rita Barcelo Program for Outreach and Extension Services. The school has active partnership with City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO). Over the years, the school through its extension program has become more involved with the agency. It is an institutional program that is dynamic, relevant and responsible to the challenge of the present times.

This program is in line with the congregation's and the school's option for the poor as well as the act of creating a harmonious school and community relations.

Statement of the Problem

This study was an attempt to assess the educational improvement needed by Federation of Day Care Workers of Iriga City for Academic Year 2015 – 2016. Similarly, it sought to have the educational profiling of the federation of Day Care workers.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the personal developments needed by the Federation of Day Care Teachers of Iriga City?
2. What are the life skills developments needed by the Federation of Day Care Teachers of Iriga City?
3. What are the educational improvements needed by the Federation of Day Care Teachers of Iriga City?
4. What educational assistance can the LCCI personnel offer to the Federation of Day Care Teachers of Iriga City?

Assumption

This study has the following assumptions:

1. That the Federation of Day Care workers of Iriga City are not all equipped with necessary skills to teach in day care centers.
2. That the Day Care workers of Iriga City are in need of educational visual aids to assist in their instructions.
3. That the personnel of LCCI can offer assistance to the Federation of Day Care Workers.

Significance of the Study

The school which works for human and community development should have a close linkage and coordination with the partner/adopted community it serves. Correspondingly, it should be aware of the present situation and needs of the recipients in order to have an effective realization and fulfillment of the outreach programs, mission and apostolate beneficial to the school and to the partner agency.

Thus, a deeper understanding and assessment of the specific needs of the agency is very indispensable for this will give the school more concrete ideas which will assist its staff and students in the planning and implementation of the most effective and needed programs of the partner agency for the next development phase.

Specifically this study will benefit the:

Day Care Workers. An avenue to have refresher and updating of the basic facilitation of skills to learners.

College (La Consolacion College). A prospect to serve and contribute to the development of its community.

Community. A chance to have a more productive citizens contributing to future development.

LCCI Personnel. An opportunity to apply all the theories taught in the classroom and for continuous search for higher learning.

Scope and Delimitation

The study was focused on the assessment of the educational needs of the Federation of Day Care workers of the different Child Development Center under the supervision of City Social Welfare and Development Office for the academic year 2015 – 2016. The respondents of the study were delimited to forty seven (47) day care workers. The respondents were given the survey questionnaire administered by the outreach coordinator.

Framework

The La Consolacion College - Iriga as a higher learning institution brings to bear in its extension programs its expertise in instruction and research. The College through the Mother Rita Barcelo Outreach Center (MRBOC) envisions developing socially aware, sensitive and responsive members of the community through active involvement in community extension activities towards community development.

The extension agenda of the school has five components which include education programs, environmental advocacy programs, empowerment programs, exposure / immersion programs and Christian formation program.

Education programs refer to organized educational activities for identified needs of specific sectors or communities with the aim of improving their conditions. Environmental advocacy program is a response to the greening program of our National Government and as mitigation to Climate Change, the Living legacy: Plant a Tree, Nurture our Future Program. This is a convergence initiative of the school wherein all pupils and students including school personnel take part in tree growing activity in their own backyards. Christian formation program, as a school rooted in Gospel values are intended to guide the formation of the whole community and an inspiration to do the works of mercy to our partner communities and agencies. Empowerment Program follows Christ teaching of *“Give man a fish, and the man will live for a day, but teach a man how to fish and then he will live for a lifetime”* wherein adopted communities are being nourished not only with the word of God, but with the necessary skill to find a source of living so as to provide their basic needs and most importantly an opportunity to live a dignified life. The Exposure Program is an avenue to raise awareness among our students to the social realities of life and its dilemma. Through exposure, we aim to engage our Augustinian students to understand others who are poor, deprived, oppressed and exploited and inculcate social roles and responsibilities as part of our vision-mission.

Planning and implementing the different extension program components through the different extension services are guided by four extension principles. The extension program should be Needs-based and guided, Core-Values oriented, ASAS mission oriented, and participatory. These principles are significant in materializing the purpose of any extension program. An extension program should stem from or at least complements an existing academic

or research program relative to the assessment, analysis, and resolution of the target group’s needs and concerns (needs-based and guided); transformative and more aligned to the ASAS pastoral priorities which are directed towards the poor, the marginalized, the indigenous peoples, and the youth and for environmental protection (ASAS mission oriented); and it seeks to holistically form students that are Compassionate, Gospel- Value oriented, intellectually competent and are open to growth (Core Values); also its engages all stakeholders which include the implementers and clientele (participatory).Figure 1 shows the MRBOC Programs and Sub-programs.

The conduct of the school extension programs follows a process. Problems should be identified first only then that specific needs of the target group are to be assessed. The results of the needs assessment serve as the basis for extension program proposal- making. Approved extension program proposal should be processed for its implementation. Once the extension program is implemented, constant monitoring should be ensured to finally meet the objectives of the program. The extension program will only be terminated if it has attained its purpose.

Figure 1 MRBOC Programs and Sub-Programs

II. METHOD AND PROCEDURE

The research method used was descriptive method.

A. Subjects

The respondents of this study were forty seven (47) day care workers or 90% of the total number of teacher recipient of the federation in Iriga City.

B. Instrument

The main data gathering tool used to collect data was the questionnaire. However, to support the information gathered through the questionnaire, an informal interview was also conducted to validate the responses of the respondents on the questionnaire. Respondents were assisted and oriented well before answering the questionnaire given.

C. Administration

The outreach coordinator attended the regular monthly meeting of the federation to administer the questionnaire and conduct interview. Respondents were assisted and oriented well before answering the questionnaire given.

D. Statistical Treatment

The data gathered by the researcher were tallied and tabulated. The statistic employed in the interpretation of the data was the weighted mean, percentage and the ranking distribution.

The responses of the survey were tabulated and assigned after computing the mean occurrence such as that:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Needed
3.50 – 4.49	Moderately Needed
2.50 – 3.49	Needed
1.50 – 2.49	Fairly Needed
1.49– and below	Not Needed

III. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA

Needs of the Day Care Teacher

The needs assessment survey was conducted last October 15, 2015 during the regular monthly meeting of the Day Care Workers held at Senior Citizen Hall, Sta. Cruz, Iriga City. The survey questionnaire was administered to the teachers by the Head of MRBOC.

After administration of the survey questionnaire, the responses were tallied and weighted mean was computed for interpretation. Table shows the needs of the Day Care teachers in terms of educational improvement.

Table I Personal Development

Needs	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Identify my strengths and weaknesses	2.98	Needed	1
2. Understand my personal values	2.93	Needed	2.5
3. Learn more about grooming and personal care	2.89	Needed	2.5
4. Discipline myself for better teaching habits	2.93	Needed	4
Average Weighted Mean	2.93	Needed	

It could be gleaned from the table that of the four needs of the Day Care teacher rank first is the identification of strengths and weaknesses with a weighted mean of 2.98 which means needed. While understanding one's personal values and disciplining oneself for better teaching habits were rated 2.93 as its weighted mean which means needed. And the need to learn more about grooming and personal care was rated with 2.89 which means needed. And the average weighted mean was 2.93 which means needed. It can be inferred that all items are needed so intervention is required for personal development of the teacher.

Table II Skills Development

Needs	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Improve my teaching skills	3.85	Moderately Needed	1
2. Learn how to stay healthy mentally, spiritually and physically	3.38	Needed	3.5
3. Awareness of social responsibility	3.38	Needed	3.5
4. Understanding the importance of work in one's life	3.64	Moderately Needed	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.56	Moderately Needed	

It can be observed from the table that of the four life skills needs of Day Care Workers rank first were the improvement of teaching skills with weighted mean of 3.85 which means moderately needed. It was followed by the need of understanding the importance of work with weighted mean of 3.64 which also means moderately needed. While the other two needs were rated 3.38 as its weighted mean which means needed. And the average weighted mean was 3.56 for skills development which means moderately needed. It can be inferred that all items are needed so intervention is required.

Table III Educational Improvement

Needs	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Various experiences and activities such as songs, games and story-telling	3.98	Moderately Needed	3
2. Activities that build children's self-esteem	3.80	Moderately Needed	4
3. Speak effectively and improve oral exercises	3.72	Moderately Needed	6
4. Improve reading techniques	3.62	Moderately Needed	7
5. Learn about technology and media literacy	4.07	Moderately Needed	1
6. Learn Visual Literacy	3.78	Moderately Needed	5
7. Learn other teaching strategies	4.04	Moderately Needed	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.86	Moderately Needed	

From the table it is noted that of the seven educational needs of Day Care Workers rank first is to learn about technology and medi literacy with weighted mean of 4.07. Followed by the need for learning other teaching strategies with weighted mean of 4.04, provision of various experiences and activities including songs, games and storytelling with weighted mean of 3.98. Promotion of activities that build children's self-esteem ranks fourth with weighted mean of 3.80. The need for visual literacy gained a weighted mean of 3.72. Improvement of reading techniques ranks last with a weighted mean of 3.62 The stated educational needs of day care Workers gatehred an average wighted mean of 3.86 which means all needs are moderately needed by the day Care workers, thus an intervention is required for the improvement of teachers.

Profile of Day Care Workers

Table I Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Number of Teachers
College Degree	23
College Level	15
High School	7

As to the Highest Educational Attainment of the Day Care Workers respondent it was identified that 23 earned a College degree, 15 College level, and 7 were High School graduates.

Table II Teaching Experience

Number of Years	Number of Teachers
1-5 years	15
6-10 years	9
11-15 years	11

16-20 years	2
21-25 years	9
More than 26 years	1

For the number of years teaching in the Day Care, 15 Day Care workers have rendered between 1-5 years of service; 9 Day Care workers rendered between 6-10 years of service; 11 Day Care workers who have rendered 11-15 years of service, 2 Day Care workers have rendered between 16-20 years of service; 9 Day Care workers who have rendered between 21-25 years of service and 1 Day Care worker who have spent 38 long years of service.

Moreover, there were 44 Day Care workers who are Roman Catholic and 3 Born Again Christian.

Proposed Intervention

The Basic Education Department were tapped to assist and spearhead the Enrichment Program for the Day Care Workers. The Coordinator of Studies and the different Subject Area Coordinator were given the results of this research and it was agreed that they shall take turns on giving intervention by subject area. And with the permission of the CSWDO Officer it was arranged that Enrichment Activity shall be conducted on a monthly basis either every 15th or last Friday of the month which is also the scheduled regular meeting of the federation for atleast three-hours per meeting. Below is the proposed class session as the intervention.

Enrichment Program Session

Language Area –	English and Filipino
Religion –	Faith Life Sharing/ Recollection
Social Studies-	Social Awareness
Science and TLE-	Computer and Technology Literacy
Mathematics-	Finacial Literacy
Mapah-	Health and Fitness
Guidance-	Personal Development

Copy of songs and hand-made big books will be provided to the Day Care teachers. This may assist them in their teaching-learning process.

Evaluation will be given to the Day Care Workers at the end or in between the Enrichment activity. This will be in form of oral and written test. The result of this evaluation will determine the achievement of the Day Care Workers and the success of the intervention and determine gaps for improvement of the outreach program.